

UNIVERSITY OF LIEGE

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

National context: Protection against violence and moral or sexual harassment at work is provided under a federal law that dates from 11 June 2002. This law is not specific to research or higher education settings, it protects all types of workers, including those working at universities and research organisations (administrative, technical, and research staff). This law provides a general framework, which is then implemented and, in some cases, further developed by some employers.

Regional context

In the French-Speaking Community (Wallonia-Brussels Federation), an inter-university committee dedicated to the promotion of gender equality in research was established by a decree (a federal level law) on 10 March 2016. It is called the Committee for Women in Science (*Comité Femmes & Sciences*) and the Academy of Research and Higher Education (ARES) serves as the Secretariat. Every university nominates a gender focal point representative, who participates in the work of the Committee for Women and Science and is responsible for publishing an annual report on the state of gender equality at the university, drafting a joint synthesis report, and increasing the visibility and sharing information about gender at the university and among the general public. After the Parliament of the French-Speaking Community passed a resolution to support higher education institutions in their fight against gender discrimination, a special Commission on Gender in Higher Education (CoGES) was created in December 2020. This Standing Commission acts as a space for crosscutting discussion on gender issues. One of the aims is to support institutions in their fight against harassment in higher education institutions and in training professionals to detect and support victims of violence.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

In conformity with the institutional policy adopted at the level of the French-Speaking Community, the university has introduced annual reporting on gender equality and has appointed a gender contact point. The university has also appointed contact persons in each faculty who form the Gender Group. More specifically regarding harassment and violence, the approach adopted by the University of Liège is to work on non-discrimination and violence in general in order to mobilise all the actors. The Student Quality of Life Service (*service qualité vie étudiante*) oversees initiatives aimed at prevention and protection through training and by instituting processes and procedures for reporting and support. The two policy documents that have been introduced by the university are Work Regulations (Règlement du travail) and, specifically for students, a Student Induction Charter (Charte baptême). The policy mix relating to GBV consists of non-dedicated policies, that is, general policies addressing GBV as a part of the policy.

URLs

- › Work Regulations: https://www.uliege.be/cms/c_11572857/en/equal-opportunities-and-gender
- › Student Induction Charter: <https://www.agel-liege.be/la-charte/>
https://www.campus.uliege.be/cms/c_11298888/fr/les-baptemes-entre-folklore-estudiantin-et-prevention

Entry into force: Both policies were introduced in 2015.

TRAINING

Targeted training activities are organised every year for specific groups, i.e. for the members of the Student Induction committee and for people in charge of student wellbeing, along with thematic training, for example, on non-violent communication.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

An interdisciplinary master's degree in gender studies has been created that draws on the combined expertise of the six universities in the Wallonia-Brussels Federation in this field by organising and jointly offering specialised courses. This master's degree offers multi- and interdisciplinary training in the field of gender studies grounded in an intersectional perspective, and GBV is one of the subjects it addresses.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The two policies combined address the following **five** forms of GBV: physical violence, psychological violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, and gender-based harassment. The Work Regulation for staff makes reference to all five, while the Student Induction Charter addresses all except sexual violence.

- Gender-Based Violence
- Physical Violence
- Psychological Violence
- Sexual Violence
- Sexual Harassment
- Gender-Based Harassment

- Economic and Financial Violence
- Stalking
- Organisational Violence
- Online Violence
- Other

7Ps covered: The two policies combined address the following **6Ps**: prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services and policy. While both policies address prevention and protection, the Work Regulation also addresses prevalence, provision of services, and policy and the Charter addresses prosecution.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Intersectionality addressed

No

Specific vulnerable groups

Not defined

Target groups

Work Regulation

Academic staff
Non-academic staff

Student Induction Charter

Students

The Work Regulation is aimed at academic and non-academic staff and the Charter is aimed at students.

Bystanders addressed: No.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: Yes, through register of complaints.

Evaluation: No information.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The Work Regulation sets out a step-by-step procedure for reporting and investigating violence among staff members.

The policy defines: who to contact, how to report, a time frame, and responsible persons/units.

Who to contact: A Trust Person or the Prevention Advisor for psychosocial aspects, Labour Inspection.

How to report: There are internal and external reporting procedures. These are mainly set out in the law, but they are also specified in the internal Work Regulation. For internal procedures, first there is an informal procedure and the possibility also to introduce a formal procedure. Informal psychosocial intervention involves the complainant and a Trust Person or a Prevention Advisor for psychosocial aspects engaging in a search for a solution through informal means, in particular through interviews (reception, active listening, and advice), an intervention with another person in the institution, or a conciliation process between the persons involved (subject to their agreement). The type of informal psychosocial intervention chosen by the complainant is recorded in a document that is dated and signed by the intervener and the complainant, who receives a copy.

Formal psychosocial intervention (Prevention Advisor for Psychosocial Aspects): If the staff member who lodges a complaint does not want to request an informal psychosocial intervention, if he/she wishes to terminate the process, or if the intervention fails, he/she can request a formal psychosocial intervention from the Prevention Advisor for psychosocial aspects. A formal intervention involves asking the employer to take the appropriate steps set out in an opinion after the specific work situation has been analysed and measures have been proposed by the Prevention Advisor for psychosocial aspects.

External procedure: A staff member who believes that he/she is being subjected to violence, mobbing, or sexual harassment at work has the right to go directly to the police or to the social inspectors of the Welfare Inspectorate, without first going through a Trust Person or a Prevention Advisor for psychosocial aspects.

The employee also has the right to bring a case directly before the Labour Inspection without going through the institution's internal procedure (informal or formal).

However, if an employee takes the case directly before a judge, the judge may order him/her to use the existing internal procedure at the University of Liège. A register of third-party events will be set up and maintained by the confidential advisor. Records in the third-party register will include

a description of the incident of violence, mobbing, or sexual harassment at work caused by other persons in the workplace that the staff member considers to have been committed, and the date of the incident. They do not include the identity of the staff member who has lodged the complaint, unless the staff member wishes to share it. Only the employer, the Prevention Advisor for psychosocial risks, the confidential advisors, and the Director of the SUPHT have access to this register.

Responsible person/units: The employer, the Prevention Advisor for psychosocial aspects, confidential advisors, and the Director of the SUPHT.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

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